

Active learning in project management: the life cycle of a virtual scientific colloquium and its impact on students' performance

Sanderson Cesar Macêdo Barbalho¹, Antônio Henrique Duarte¹, Kerlla de Souza Luz²

¹ Department of Production Engineering, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil

² Department of Exact Sciences, Federal District University Center

Email: sandersoncesar@unb.br, duarteantoniohenrique@gmail.com, kerlla.luz@udf.edu.br

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Abstract

The industrial engineering course at the University of Brasília runs through a project-based learning approach. The course is framed in 12 semesters. In the third semester, a project management discipline prepares students for totally project-based disciplines starting in the fourth semester. Teaching project management and dealing with the complexity of relations involved in the running project with undergraduates that must solve unstructured problems in a short period is challenging. Is it enough to expose the content in lectures? If we had a normal context without the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, we probably would perform group activities, but it is not possible in pandemic times. After the first half of the discipline, teachers decide to set a virtual project effort to make a virtual colloquium in Project Management. It was a way for students to experience a real project and deal with the diversity of competencies necessary to succeed. The paper presents the discipline structure, the project decisions regarding the endeavor to plan, execute, monitor, and control the Colloquium, and the results regarding student content assessment. Results demonstrate worse grades for the final content evaluation when compared to the first assessment. Despite this, students were satisfied, and the Colloquium was successful with speakers from Brazil and abroad, more than 300 subscribers.

Keywords: Project-based learning; Engineering Education; Project management; Event management; COVID-19.

1 Introduction

In the last 30 years, studies in engineering education have pointed to a change in the educational landscape: away from the rationality that values objectivity, and the linear curriculum focused only on technical learning. This new scenario seeks an educational paradigm that supports the holistic approach necessary for student development (TALGAR, 2017).

Although prior research has shown that active learning can be especially effective for educating a diverse student body while increasing the retention rate of students in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) programs DeMonbrun et al. (2017), in Brazil, most engineering educators do not believe in such methodologies. It is noteworthy that teaching approaches based on lectures remain dominant in engineering education, leaving graduates poorly prepared to understand the complexities of the engineering profession (ASEE, 2009). The lecture-based approach emphasizes procedural knowledge and cannot maintain attention, leading to low attendance rates (MILLS et al., 2003). It means that students may not be motivated to go to class and retain classroom information that emphasizes memorization and recall. It is problematic since memorization, rather than applying knowledge, does not allow students to see what is being taught in the classroom. It contributes to the high dropout rate in engineering courses in Brazil, which is almost 50%, according to the Brazilian Association of Engineering Education (ABENGE, 2018).

Reis et al. (2017) mention several studies that demonstrate the advantages of the results achieved by students using active methodologies. According to Ríos et al. (2010), under an active learning framework, the student leaves the passive role of just receiving the knowledge to take an active role in learning. According to Downing (2001), professional skills are increasingly valued, i.e., companies value skills beyond technical knowledge and specialization. The attempt to innovate in educational practices in Engineering eventually originated new teaching methods around the world. Engineering faculties are increasingly considering the merits of the practical application of knowledge, internalized in the content of disciplines, and before graduation. It is understood as fundamental that engineers develop proficiency beyond technique but include interdisciplinary

skills such as cooperation and project management (Taajamaa et al., 2013). In this sense, problem-based learning and project-based learning, both commonly called PBL, have been widely applied as teaching and learning strategies (Lin et al., 2014; Jeon et al., 2014; De Los Ríos-Carmenado et al., 2015; Barbalho et al., 2017).

The University of Brasília (UnB) implemented an innovative undergraduate course in Industrial Engineering in 2009, intending to improve the retention of students' knowledge and better relating theory with practice, adopting a methodology with student empowerment (Prince & Felder, 2006; Lima et al., 2012; Zindel et al., 2012). Based on the PBL approach, the course aims to foster the skills of undergraduate students to deal with real-world problems involved in specific projects that aim to solve a current problem of some company or organization.

This work analyzed a project-based learning activity (PjBL) that integrated the current moment of remote teaching requirement according to COVID-19 with an event proposed within a discipline of UnB's industrial engineering course. A project management colloquium was organized, where the preparation of the entire event was distributed among the students in a team format, maintaining an organization and planning around the project management of the event. In the impossibility of performing face-to-face group activities, the Colloquium allowed students to experience a project with real results, a target audience, responsibilities with stakeholders, time constraints, premises that should be obeyed, and risks to be mitigated.

This paper presents the Colloquium experience and its impact on the students' content evaluations comparing the two tests performed in the discipline. After this introductory section, a chapter presents the main concepts addressed. Section three presents the methodology used in the research. Section four presents the case studied. The article is closed with the final considerations and conclusive elements of stakeholders' perceptions, time constraints, premises that should be obeyed, and risks to be mitigated.

2 Project-based Learning

The Methodology of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) originated in 1959 when the American philosopher and educator John Dewey (1859-1952) proved to learn from the practice of doing, valuing, questioning, and contextualizing the ability of students to think gradually to acquire a relative knowledge to solve real situations in projects related to content in the area of studies (Caldeira et al., 2017). Thus, it is observed that the PjBL is associated with constructivist theories, which aim to allow students to conduct their learning through research and work collaboratively to research and create projects that reflect their knowledge (Bell, 2010). In addition to providing the collection of new viable technological skills until they become proficient communicators and advanced problem solvers, students benefit from this instruction approach (Luz, 2019).

According to Krajcik & Blumenfeld (2000), meaningful learning occurs when the learner actively builds his understanding based on his experience and interaction with the world. Thus, it can be based on the perspective that learning, from basic to graduate education, can be subsidized by a continuous process that will require the student to have a constant reconstruction every time he can acquire and abstract new experiences (Luz et al., 2019).

The learning environment conducted through active methodologies (PBL and PjBL) creates cognitive learning through their actions (Hmello-Silver et al. 2006). For Balve & Albert (2015), the PjBL's approach increases individual motivation and presents students with a real demand that needs to be met. In the PjBL approach, students develop their knowledge through active learning, interactions with the external environment, and teamwork in collaboration, with the complementary guidance of the faculty (Taajamaa et al., 2013). When project-based education covers the entire curriculum, it is called Project-Led Education (PLE) (Lima et al., 2007; Crosthwaite et al., 2006).

There are several studies on the use of the PjBL approach. This learning methodology, covering technical and transversal skills, requires applying skills that can be characterized as "How to do". It is necessary to apply knowledge in practical contexts (Soares et al., 2013). According to the Project Management Institute (2017), the main "soft competencies" for successful project realization are leadership and influence, team building, motivation, communication, decision making, political and cultural awareness, negotiation, trust-building,

conflict management, and coaching. Project management literature has demonstrated how critical are these abilities and attitudes in real-world projects (Barbalho et al., 2019; Irfan, 2021).

Previous research at the University of Brasília has demonstrated that students have succeeded when defining their projects' scope (Barbalho et al., 2017). It also points to good knowledge conversion throughout the projects (Reis et al., 2018) with a special focus on soft skills, such as negotiation and teamwork. Luz et al. (2021) also identify teamwork as an important ability in the industrial engineering disciplines at the University of Brasília. The authors also suggest that these experiences deliver better leadership skills and a stronger attitude regarding curiosity and interest in technical contents: these previous research approaches, respectively, production planning and control, and new product development disciplines. The present work is an evaluation of the project management discipline of the Industrial Engineering syllabus.

3 Methodology

This research utilizes a case study approach (Yin, 2001). A deeper analysis is performed regarding an object of investigation, a project management course structured according to the PjBL approach in the virtual context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Qualitative and quantitative data was gathered, the latter using grading datasheets and the former by registering the reflections of the course's faculties, who are also the authors of this study. These reflections were used for understanding the results of the analysis in the form to triangulate data.

The grading data sheet was used to calculate descriptive statistics regarding the case study. A comparison between the students' grades at the initial and final exams, respectively applied before and after the Colloquium, and an evaluation of each student's participation in the colloquium organization and assistance, allow authors to wonder about the practical results of the virtual project-based learning approach applied.

The research hypothesis was that the practical approach of organizing a Colloquium with internationally recognized professionals in project management would motivate students to perform better in the final exam. Once in the first half of the course, the students presented apathy and underperformance.

4 Case Study

4.1 Context

In the Industrial Engineering curricula of the University of Brasília, the PjBL approach is addressed by a set of disciplines called production system design (PSD). Each PSD discipline is related to one or more technical disciplines in a specific semester, and projects are carried out according to the content of their respective anchor disciplines. The discipline involves resolving practical problems of private or public companies with specific project management methodologies (Figure 1). This approach stimulates students' learning by searching for solutions and project proposals to address the concrete issues that afflict partner companies. No technical content is covered before each PSD course. Their anchor disciplines are taught in the form of co-requirement. As the deeper concepts and techniques are commonly programmed for the last classes, students usually learn in a self-taught way. The teacher's support, concepts, and techniques are needed to achieve the design solutions. As every PSD discipline runs as a project, a previous course supports the necessary knowledge for students to plan, execute and control their projects. This discipline is called Production System Design Methodology (PSDM) and is highlighted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General structure of University of Brasilia's Industrial Engineering program. Adapted form Barbalho et al. (2017).

The PSDM course is related to Project Management (PM). It is the unique mandatory discipline where students face project management knowledge, according to Project Management Institute (2017), as well as theories related to agile project management and organizational project management (Schwaber, 2004; Barbalho et al., 2019). Although the students in the PSDM course are asked to discuss real projects, the course's main focus is theoretical. In 2020 the first semester, the original proposal was built before the COVID-19 pandemic. It was planned to have two exams and a group activity to present PM tools and techniques applied in real-world projects. After the pandemic, the professor planned work only on the theoretical side of the previous plan. Still, after the first exam and joint with the assistant teachers, he proposed a real project to allow students to experience a project by themselves. The best way to do that would be through an event. All students, 55, had to participate as the event staff and also attendees.

4.1 The Project Management Colloquium

The Research Group on Innovation, Projects and Processes (GIIPP) had organized in 2019 the I Project Management Colloquium of the University of Brasília. The concept of the GP Colloquium was to conduct an in-depth scientific discussion on project management in the Federal District, given its potential impact on well-managed projects throughout the country. The Colloquium was thought to be face-to-face, having participated international researchers in GP.

The 2nd Project Management Colloquium maintained the same concept, but it was completely virtual. It had the participation of national and international speakers with great experience in project management and academic research, uniting the scientific world with good management practices. The event gathered in two days more than 350 entries from Brazil and abroad. It supported and participated in project management, education, innovation, and product development, emphasizing the aviation company EMBRAER and the Project Management Institute (PMI) Brazil Chapters.

4.2 Dynamics of Colloquium

The Colloquium aimed to teach the practice of project management to students. A scope and work breakdown structure (WBS) was elaborated up to the work package level by the teacher and his research assistant by way of prior preparation. Next, the WhatsApp tool was used to create workgroups with students. These groups were divided according to the second level of the WBS (the large deliveries to be made). The students there held the meetings to detail the planning and coordinate the division and execution of the work resulting from the delivery (the work packages). A WhatsApp group was also created with all students for general and instant project coordination. For the availability of the scope, WBS, deliveries, and other guidelines of the event's organization, we used the unified platform of communication, collaboration, and file storage, Microsoft Teams. All these virtual spaces were monitored and accompanied by the teacher and his assistant. They constantly fed students with new tasks, performed course corrections, and invested in the students' motivation, encouraging the commitment and dedication of each working group.

Figure 2. Work Breakdown Structure of Project Management Colloquium

As stated earlier, the conduct of the discipline also took place online, and the videoconferences were held on the Microsoft Teams Platform. The discipline, coordination, availability of didactic content, and notes' availability were held in the Online Platform Google Classroom. In the online classes of the discipline were passed the contents of project management necessary to realize the event and the meetings of Kickoff Meeting, coordination and general monitoring of the project during the class hours were held. During the week, the event occurred on two days, sequentially, in the evening, between 19:00 and 21:40 hours. The objective of these choices was to allow students' participation, who also attended other subjects during the day. The event had the program presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Colloquium Ageda: Keynotes and Lectures

Colloquium Agenda		
	Keynote	Lecture
DAY 1	André B. Barcaui Post-doctor in Administration from FEA/USP, Ph.D. in Administration from UNR, Master in Management Systems from UFF, with a degree in Information Technology and Psychology. Founding member of PMI Chapter Rio, coordinator of the MBA in Project Management and Information Technology Management at the Getulio Vargas Foundation (FGV).	Agility in project and business
	Prof. Sanderson Barbalho, Ph.D. in Mechanical Engineering from the University of São Paulo, Adjunct Professor in the Department of Production Engineering at the University of Brasília, and coordinator of the Research Group on Innovation, Projects, and Processes (GIPIP).	Project Management Research at UNB
	Júlio Cesar, Program Administrator Engineer of the EMBRAER team, won the PMI award in the USA as the best project of the year 2019.	Requirements Management of the E-jets E2 Program
DAY 2	Darli Vieira (Ph.D.) and Alencar Bravo (Ph.D.) Professors at Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières (UQTR), Quebec, Canada Research Chair in Management of Aeronautical Projects Chaire de recherche en Gestion de Projets Aéronautiques.	The consolidation of the Chair in Management of Aeronautical Projects.
	Anderson Sales Specialist in Disciplined Agile and Governance Advisor of PMI São Paulo - Brazil.	Requirements Management in the agile look
	Ernani Marques, Partner & founder of ATHEM Consulting and Training, represents the British line of project management, program, and portfolio in Brazil.	PRINCE2 Product-Based Planning

On the day of the event, the professor, his research assistant, and a professional guest ceremonialist held the presentation because of the notoriety and seniority of national and international speakers. However, the entire

backstage run was performed by the students. Tasks such as monitoring the speakers, facilitating their access to the tool and removing doubts; the execution of the co-host function in the event of the internet fall of the main host; the support for the solution of technical problems of all order, the control of the access of the enrollees, the monitoring of open microphones to silence them, among others, were all fully implemented by the students.

The event, according to the enrollees and students of the discipline, was a great success. The online form of realization allowed the presentation of an interesting grid of subjects by renowned national and international speakers; allowed the registration of participants from all over the country and abroad, exponentially increasing the number of total entries concerning the first Colloquium. The second Colloquium had more than 300 subscribers. Some lectures registered more than 100 attendees online.

The use of students in the planning and execution of tasks allowed the increase of the project's scope, both in terms of organization but mainly in terms of dissemination and scope. The pedagogical aspect allowed the students to practice theoretical knowledge acquired in project management and senior professionals' access to the project management market. It was made clear among them the feeling of having participated in a really special project/discipline.

4.3 Colloquium evaluation methodology

The Colloquium was evaluated through the participation of students in the activities, and for this purpose, the KAA methodology was used (Luz et al., 2019). The items evaluated and their respective weights are shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Evaluated Attitudes

Interest and Curiosity	Evaluate how the student positions himself/herself in his/her engagement in the event. The results of a study commissioned by the Institute for the Future (ITF) show that all organizations and businesses will be technology-based in the next decade, requiring companies to rethink current models of infrastructure and ways of working (DELL, 2017).
Proactivity	Evaluate the student's ability to effectively resolve (group) deliveries of the proposed project activities. It is adapting the project and following Almeida (2000) perspective that indicates the importance of perceiving the probability of the emergence of a problem before it even happens.
Commitment and Ethics	It consists of evaluating the student's bond with the project, based on Borges' idea (2007), according to which commitment is understood as creating the employees' bond with their respective organizations. This conception can represent the students who remained in the project even though they could lock the discipline and not participate in realizing the project. It consists of the evaluation of Borges (2007) represents the codes of ethics through a set of elements that characterize people's behavior within a social group. In virtual classes, the student's social behavior within the working groups, the unified communication platform, and social media was evaluated.

As illustrated later, the students' attitudes towards the Colloquium were captured through their participation in the event preparation and execution dynamics. Table 3 presents the skills analyzed.

Table 3. Evaluated Skills

Leadership	The ability of the student to exert influence on the group. Khoury (2018) cites a comprehensive list of topics related directly to leadership and indicates communication as the most important tool for exercising leadership.
Teamwork	For Hardingham (2000), in a professional work team, at least one goal can only be achieved by all involved. Here it is about evaluating the student's ability to work in partnership with other team members. Teamwork was evaluated in the performance of activities within WhatsApp working groups, interactions and execution of activities on the Microsoft Teams platform, creating and maintaining social media, and conducting/executing the to days of the event.
Collaboration and Cooperation	Collaboration is seen only as of the act of involvement and sharing of information. Cooperation is observed by participation in the group's activities, where the individual is present whenever necessary (ODELIUS, 2016). The student's performance was evaluated during the kickoff meeting, follow-up meeting, end-up meetings; in the working groups on WhatsApp and during the event, together with the group, interacting in the activities carried out are examples where collaboration and cooperation between students could be evaluated.

Communication	Today there are specific methods to conquer the space increasingly idealized by creative communication that meets the most varied needs in the universe of human relations (PONTE, 2000). Here, it evaluates the student's ability to clarify doubts with their questions and answers when questioned. Ability to organize ideas when talking about deliverables' progress, communicate on social networks, workgroups, and open spaces for questions during the event.
Critical Analysis	Evaluate the student individually regarding their critical perception (evaluative) about the stages of the project and the decisions made by the team. Students who resist express themselves or who do not contribute to their group may find it difficult to give opinions.

The following constructive aspects of the Colloquium were used to identify the students' skills and attitudes regarding the event:

- Participation in the Colloquium (event), as a spectator or working in the assistance of some activity;
- Participation in meetings in the virtual classroom. Learning content, taking questions, as well as performing status presentations of project deliveries;
- Performing deliveries of activities, whether planning, organizing, or executing the Colloquium. Effecting the delivery;
- Participation in WhatsApp groups for coordination and development of deliveries;
- Registration in the social networks created for the event (event website, Whatsapp, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn).
- Participation and performance (dissemination, interaction, posts) on social networks of dissemination of the event (event website, WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn);
- Participation in the unified communication and collaboration platform (Microsoft Teams) for the coordination, registration, and realization of deliveries

Table 4 lists the attitudes and skills analyzed to infer the Colloquium students' participation score with the evaluation moments presented above.

Table 4. Applied Evaluation Model of the PSDM Discipline in 2.2020.

		(1) Participation in the Colloquium (event)	(2) Participation in meetings in the virtual classroom	(3) Realization of the Deliveries of activities	(4) Participation in WhatsApp groups	(5) Registration on the social networks of the event	(6) Participation and performance in the social networks of the event	(7) Participation in the Microsoft Teams platform
Attitudes	Interest and Curiosity							
	Proactivity							
	Commitment and Ethics							
Skills	leadership							
	Teamwork							
	Collaboration and Cooperation							
	communication							

The next section presents an analysis of the grades obtained by the students in this teaching and learning process, considering the 1st test performed by the students in which the classes were positive using a virtual environment, the final score of participation of the Colloquium, and the grade of the final test of the discipline.

4.4 Results

Table 5 presents the descriptive analysis of the students' grades.

Table 5. Final grades

	Exam 1	Attitudes	Abilities	Colloquium	Exam 2
Average	6,84	8,40	7,72	9,06	5,94
Standard deviation	2,10	1,76	1,72	1,59	1,79
Maximum	10,00	10,00	10,00	10,00	9,70
Minimum	2,40	1,00	1,00	0,00	2,70

As presented in Table 5, the second exam had fewer grades than the first one, even after the workgroup represented by the Colloquium. Table 6 presents the correlations between these data.

Table 6. Correlation between grades

	Exam 1	Attitudes	Abilities	Colloquium	Exam 2
Exam 1	1				
Attitudes	0,043	1			
Abilities	0,016	0,958	1		
Colloquium	0,214	0,877	0,844	1	
Exam 2	0,333	0,146	0,212	0,134	1

As presented in Table 6, there was no correlation between exams and the Colloquium results. The Colloquium grade is only associated with the attitudes and skills analyzed.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This paper presents a case study where a virtual team practice was proposed in a Project Management discipline. Still, no results were realized regarding a better knowledge apprehension by students, as captured in an exam, and the attitudes or abilities diagnosed as highlighted in the case.

This result was not expected but brought reflections concerning project-based learning approaches regarding students' knowledge in these educational practices. The fact is that the second exam had as a focus some techniques for project management planning and control, especially for scope and time management. Then, the most worked skills and attitudes that the teaching group implemented for training students and the planning and execution of PM colloquium were not evaluated on the second exam. Instead, the exam was technical-based, developing well-done work breakdown structures and critical path analysis. These contents belong to the hard part of PM knowledge.

For more consistency to evaluate a project like this, it could be better to assess the students' motivation after the first and second parts of the discipline. Some questions on the second exam could be addressed to evaluate if the practice of PM Colloquium has reinforced any soft skills evaluated on the first exam. Finally, the Colloquium could be prepared actively using work breakdown structures and project schedules to align it with the technical content taught in the second part of the PSDM course.

Future studies will analyze the following Colloquiums and improve the data gathering approach, not only in attitudes and abilities but also the knowledge element of the KAA framework. The same content of the PSDM discipline will be applied without the PM Colloquium to advance reflections on the impact of virtual project-based learning on engineering education.

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